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ETHNIC IDENTITY – A STRATEGIC RESOURCE OF THE STATE

Анотація. Життя етнічних меншин у державі з іншою культурою та традиціями непросте. Будь-який народ відрізняється своєю культурою, історією, звичаями та характером. Їх згаданий індивідуалізм у випадку співжиття з іншим народом потребує розуміння й поміркованого злиття з особливостями іншого народу. Співіснування двох і більше народів може спричинити труднощі, а в окремих випадках і виникнення конфліктних вогнищ.

У статті на прикладі різних країн і на основі різних теорій ми продемонстрували важливість етнічної ідентичності етнічних меншин для держави. А також важливість і вплив політичної культури. Ми розглянули роль інтернаціоналізму та мультикультуралізму, позитивні сторони та ризики можливих негативних наслідків для держав в результаті їх впровадження. У статті на основі досліджень грузинських дослідників, спираючись на чинне законодавство Грузії та державні пріоритети описано стратегію грузинської держави щодо процесів інтеграції етнічних меншин та їхньої етнічної ідентичності.

Abstract. The integration and identity of ethnic minorities in the states is significantly influenced by the discussion of the theory of interculturalism. Cultural and social integration of ethnic minorities is one of the most important factors for any state. On the basis of intercultural education, it is possible for nations with different origins and cultures to connect with each other with positive attitudes. Intercultural development is a direction focused on the unity of nations, which is distinguished by its positivity, taking into account common interests and rights. However, the problem of possible assimilation, which is directed against the identity of nations, is worth noting. In contrast to the mentioned theory, in the article we discuss multiculturalism, which is focused on the formation of individualism and identity of ethnic minorities as nations, while striving for individualism and isolation can lead to negative attitudes and disconnection in society, which increases the risks of internal conflict in the state. As for the problem of intercultural dialogue, this is also a topical issue among ethnic minorities. We will discuss the positive dynamics of the problem in the article on the example of Georgia. The article discusses the role of political culture, civil culture, education reform and media in relation to ethnic minorities.

Key words: Ethnic identity, ethnic minorities, state strategy, political resources, integration.

The identity of the ethnic minorities is determined by the preservation of the traditions, cultural values and customs of the ethnic minorities.

Ethnic identity is a national value that must be protected by the state, whose full citizens are its own ethnic minorities, and the protection of these rights must be carried out by legislation that puts any citizen of the state on equal terms, regardless of their national religious or cultural value. Regardless of the differences of the ethnic minorities with the local nation, their rights should be protected by the state and any element of discrimination should be eliminated by legal regulations. Representatives of ethnic minorities should consider themselves full citizens of any country of which they are citizens.

The introduction and development of intercultural and multicultural political models in the states is noteworthy in relation to ethnic minorities. The multicultural model serves the purpose of preserving the identity of many nations, according to which the ethnic minorities demand the protection of their rights, culture and traditions based on the theory, the probability of the ideological speeches of the mentioned ethnic groups leads to a group of negatively disposed society, which can be formed into a less manageable wave against the state, and the probability of their management by the state become a problematic issue.

As for the intercultural model, as we have already mentioned, it is the unity of the common values of different nations, which is acceptable to each one, it serves the principle of harmonious life of diverse ethnic groups living together, although the dangers of neglecting national identity and the possible assimilation problem, which is directed against the identity of nations, are high. An interesting example of the rapprochement of the nations is France, where, along with the French, there are various ethnic groups of Africans, Germans, Jews, Basques, Muslims, and Southeast Asians. To overcome the problem of multicultural dialogue, it is necessary to focus on the common interests of diverse ethnic groups, a clear example of this is the United States of America.

The protection of the rights of ethnic minorities should be regulated by the protection of the interest of each citizen in the state from a legal obligation. Strategic plans of democratic countries in relation to ethnic minorities are increasingly focused on protecting their rights. Thus, the existing dynamic process in democratic countries will uniquely protect the rights of ethnic minorities if their fundamental problems - language, public socialization, basic education etc. - will be overcome with state support. The integration of ethnic minorities as a separate problem in the near future may not be a serious topic of political anxiety, it will definitely be replaced by the topic of integration of citizens, which will not be determined by national and religious differences, but by the protection of the rights of each person, whose rights are regulated by law. Integration of citizens is an important aspect of civic culture that is a high priority for contemporary world politics.

If we look at the 2022-2030 plan for the integration of ethnic minorities in Georgia, it will become clear to expect high opportunities for the integration of ethnic minorities.

The issue of the identity of ethnic minorities in Georgia has been protected for years both on the basis of legal regulations and on the basis of public understanding. According to the current statistical data, the low rate of ethno-cultural alienation in relation to the state of ethnic minorities is clear. Issues of intercultural dialogue among ethnic minorities, whose integration is partly related to difficulty and suffers from the consequences of lack of communication and language barrier, are under study.

It is worth noting that the country is dynamically and consistently taking important steps for the progressive results of civil equality; for the preservation of the cultural identity of each nation and for the introduction of legislative innovations that will ensure the rights of every citizen of Georgia, regardless of their differences from a religious, national or other point of view. In the

current process of civil integration, there are frequent challenges, the correct response to which will inevitably lead to the transformation of ethnic minorities into a full-fledged civil society.

Integration of citizens is one of the important issues for the political life of any country. The integration of citizens is necessary for the development of civil culture in this country. The citizen of each country should be integrated in the society where he/she lives. Time changes everything, including society, countries, citizens, and so on. As Gabriel Almond would say, Western societies change, whether being approved or not. Modernist society, despite its strength, is replaced by postmodern one, characterized by the autonomy and diversity of people, individuals in exchange for hierarchy and conformity. A cultural change that actually resulted from generational change brought about by new life experiences and a different reality. It is worth noting that the truth propagated by the dominant elite has a great influence on the society, but the life experience of ordinary people is also important, and in the end may even have more trust in ordinary people (than the truth presented in official form). The opinion presented on the basis of Gabriel Almond's research demonstrates the necessity of socialization and integration of people based on the relations of different nations, which determines the formation of civil culture.

Almond and Verba in their book "The Civic Culture – Political Attitudes and Democracy in Five Nations" describe the results of their own research in five countries, the main focus of which is political culture. According to the authors, civil culture is the basis without which the proper functioning of the democratic system is impossible. Such a cultural context emerged from the blending of old and new cultures in the United States and Great Britain and includes elements of both countries. On the one hand, it is participatory and open to innovations, and on the other hand, it is moderate and cautious. The old will somehow merge and neutralize the new. Scientists often explain the reason for the formation of civil culture by the course of historical events. Also, historical analysis is often referred to while studying other countries where a similar culture did not develop.³ Almond and Verba chose a less subjective research method in order to obtain quantitative and reliable data. Their goal was to determine the characteristics of attitudes and behaviors in democratic countries and compare them with those in other countries. As a result of the analysis, the authors identified four dimensions to which orientation was the subject of their interest. These are: 1. The knowledge that an individual has of his/her own country, its political system, location, power, constitution, and similar matters. Also, his/her feelings and opinions/assessments regarding these matters⁴. 2. The knowledge that an individual has about the structures and roles, the political elite, and the initiatives involved in the input process. It also means his/her feelings and opinions with regard to these structures. 3. Knowledge, feelings and evaluations that the individual has about the output process and the structures involved in it. 4. An individual's perception of himself/herself as a part of the political system. The extent to which he/she knows his/her own rights, powers, obligations and strategies

³ Almond, G., and Verba, S. (1989). *The civic culture revisited*. p. 34.

⁴ See there

for gaining power. How he/she feels about his/her abilities. What norms of engagement and behavior he/she recognizes and uses during political reasoning and opinion formation⁵.

Civil integration is an important aspect of civil culture, the weak link of civil integration in our country can be said to be related to representatives of ethnic minorities. In terms of social development, the rate of their involvement in certain regions is still quite low, which in turn creates a complex picture of problems.

The development of civil culture is reflected by the increasing trends of integration in relation to ethnic minorities, which was reflected in numerous works of Georgian researchers based on statistical data and various observations. According to Mikheil Shavtvaladze⁶, a number of measures have been taken by the state for the process of civil integration of ethnic minorities, the reforms carried out for public involvement and to overcome the language problem, the trends of ethnic minorities' involvement in politics, the increasing political activity of the Azerbaijani population living in Kvemo Kartli in the 2016 and subsequent parliamentary elections are noteworthy. According to Shavtvaladze's analysis, the passive political interest in the past was due to the language problem of the ethnic minorities, the ethnic groups living in Georgia were less informed about the electoral legislation and the political electoral system of Georgia. A significant increase in the political participation of the ethnic minority in the elections should be conditioned by the actual circumstances of the generational change. In addition, the increase of the number of non-Georgian-speaking students in Georgian universities, which was promoted as a result of the reforms implemented in educational programs, is of great significance. As a result of statistical research from 2003 to 2019, the number of non-Georgian-speaking students increased from 300 to 2000, it is worth noting that the growth trend is increasing. The educational reform led to an increase in the knowledge of the Georgian language among the minorities. In addition, raising the awareness of ethnic minorities uniquely determined the integration of minority representatives into Georgian society and politics, especially among young members of the community. The representation of ethnic minorities in the legislative body has also grown, which indicates the increasing trend of integration.

Ghia Nodia's work "The Polyethnicity of Georgia: The Fact, The Attitude Towards the Fact and Thoughts for Political Strategy" is worth mentioning in order to explain the problem of low involvement and integration of ethnic minorities.⁷ The work deals with the problems of education, barriers of social communication and a number of specific examples, such as preschool education, problems of non-Georgian schools, the problem of the state language, which causes many other problems due to low communication ability, access to state services, etc.

⁵ See there

⁶ Shavtvaladze, M. *Consociational Democratic Model in the Post-Soviet Multi-Ethnic State*. TSU Publishing House, Tbilisi, 2019, p. 2.

⁷ Nodia, G. *Civil Society Development in Georgia: Achievements and Challenges*. Tbilisi, 2005.

Zviad Abashidze's work "Ethnic Minorities and Civic Integration in Georgia"⁸ is important, where the main challenges and problematic aspects in relation to ethnic minorities are well presented, according to his explanation, the main problems of integration in the territories inhabited by ethnic minorities are of various kinds, separation from the current processes inside the country leads to an informational vacuum of ethnic minorities. This is specifically due to the low level of social and general education of the different ethnic groups living in the country, the difficult economic background and the problem of intercultural dialogue, as well as the language barrier, which also determines the problem of receiving information from the media. For the purpose of integration, it is necessary to take effective steps, in particular, we need educational tools that ensure simple learning of the state language, the existence of appropriate educational institutions for the non-Georgian speaking population, which will allow them to receive a qualified education. The role of local self-governments is important, by organizing cultural events and various social activities, to ensure the rapprochement of nations and to minimize the problems of alienation of various people. Different types of communication activities will encourage ethnic minorities to get closer to local residents. Effective steps taken by the state to implement intercultural policy will significantly contribute to raising the level of involvement of ethnic minorities. In the process of integration, the role of the media is very important, in order to promote the process of democratization, it is necessary to inform the population about the current events in the country, the absence of the media creates an information vacuum, the less informed population often lacks common sense, which can lead to undesirable consequences, in relation to a number of important and specific issues. A developed state needs a developed civil society, whose objective analysis and complete freedom of access to information lead to a positive attitude towards the state and the possibility of building democracy.

The state needs to ensure the establishment of a consensual political culture society, the main goal of which will be the construction of a Georgian state equipped with strong, solid democratic institutions.

The protection of the rights of ethnic minorities and their involvement in political and social processes is of crucial importance for democratic development and the creation of an inclusive society.

Ethnic problems are quite a familiar fact for the society of any epoch. In today's modern society, people agree on the need for peaceful coexistence and the establishment of liberal ideas. However, the problems of ethnic minorities could not be fully resolved. It is often difficult for different people to integrate, and much has been said and written about it, but the problem that exists is of different kinds and mainly stems from "increasing emigration"⁹. Different countries have different attitudes and approaches towards ethnic minorities, I will try to discuss

⁸ Abashidze, Z. *Ethnic Minorities and Civil Integration Issues in Georgia*. TSU Publishing House, Tbilisi, 2011.

⁹ Abashidze, Z. *Ethnic Minorities and Civil Integration Issues in Georgia*. TSU Publishing House, Tbilisi, 2011, p. 24.

the experience of several countries. The Canadian model is one of the interesting examples among them. Canada is a settlement of diverse people, ethnic groups with different cultures. "According to the data of the 2011 national general survey, Canada is a nation with an ethno-cultural mosaic, more than 200 ethnic origins were recorded, 13 ethnic origins exceeded 1 million in 2011"¹⁰. An established form of multiculturalism in Canada implies the existence of various different ethnic minorities, the first legislation on multiculturalism was passed in 1974 in the Canadian province of Saskatchewan, as amended in 1983, the act defines multiculturalism as the right of diverse people to maintain the individuality of their own cultures. In Canada, the relevance of the said legislation was unequivocal, and almost all provinces, in addition to a few municipal governments, adopted policies of multiculturalism defined by legislative innovations. The settlement of Ontario, Canada has a multicultural policy, this policy defines the active involvement of all Intarians in public life and their activity. The Government of Ontario reaffirmed the following principles of multiculturalism policy in 1987: "Commitment to ensure that people of all cultures and backgrounds have equal access to and participation as responsible citizens"¹¹.

The American model is one of the interesting models from the point of view of ethnic minorities. In American ethnic diversity, a particular quantitative growth trend is felt in the Jewish population, and other ethnic groups are also growing, with four distinct minority groups concentrated in Los Angeles, Honolulu, Miami, San Antonio, and several other metropolises. The United States of America is the most visible in the world in terms of the combination of different ethnicities and cultural diversity. Acceptance of different cultures and people is not alien to the country, and it tries to protect the rights of its citizens with legal principles, however, according to some viewpoints, America does not know all the cultural groups of its country well. It is worth noting that the famous term "melting pot" of the United States of America has been replaced by the term "salad bowl" (Nittle, 2018). "In a salad bowl, unlike a melting pot, its ingredients and components are better visible and clearly express the idea: unity in diversity"¹².

Switzerland is also one of the outstanding countries in Europe in terms of multi-ethnicity, the problem of integration in this country is less, there are less difficulties in terms of language or politics, although the country definitely remembers a number of ethno-conflicts in the course of history, although in recent history Switzerland has successfully developed multiculturalism and it is based on two important motives. "Switzerland refused to create a culturally homogeneous nation state, instead becoming a multicultural nation from the beginning of its modern existence. Second, Switzerland has been able to create an image of democracy that promotes the sharing of political power between different cultural groups. This has led to social and political integration, peace, conflict resolution through negotiations"¹³. In Germany, the protection of the rights and interests of ethnic minorities is served by the Framework Convention

¹⁰ *Immigration and Ethnocultural Diversity in Canada*. 2018. p. 57.

¹¹ See there

¹² Abashidze, 2011, p. 34.

¹³ Linder, W., & Steffen, I. (2006). *Ethnic Structure, Inequality and Governance in the Public Sector in Switzerland*.

for the Protection of National Minorities, which entered into force in 1998, it "prohibits discrimination against members of national minorities and against their will". In addition, it obliges member states to protect the rights of freedom and provide broad support measures in favor of national minorities¹⁴.

CONCLUSION

Ethnic identity is an important factor for ethnic minorities living in any state, although studies have shown that the most important thing, along with the protection of human rights, is a high rate of integration of citizens, which is regulated by law in any country. Ethnic minorities in the state should not be discriminated, they should definitely have common values and appreciations in the multi-ethnic core so that their individualism is not violated and they are not threatened with the problem of assimilation.

References

- Nodia, G. (2005). *Civil Society Development in Georgia: Achievements and Challenges*, Tbilisi.
- Abashidze, Z. (2011). *Ethnic Minorities and Civil Integration Issues in Georgia*. TSU Publishing House, Tbilisi.
- Khundadze, T. (2016). *Main Specifications of Georgian Political Culture*. TSU Publishing House, Tbilisi.
- Shavtvaladze, M. (2019). *Consociational Democratic Model in the Post-Soviet Multi-Ethnic State*. TSU Publishing House, Tbilisi.
- On approval of the 2021–2030 state strategy for civil equality and integration and the 2021–2022 action plan of the 2021-2030 state strategy for civil equality and integration, Resolution of the Government of Georgia N356, Tbilisi, 2021.6.
- Immigration and Ethnocultural Diversity in Canada. (2018) 34. Leman, M. (1999) Canadian multiculturalism. Retrieved July 1, 2019, from.
- Linder, W. & Steffen, I. (2006). *Ethnic Structure, Inequality and Governance in the Public Sector in Switzerland. National minorities and language groups in Germany*. (2018).
- National minorities and language groups in Germany. Legal bases of the minority policy*. (2013).
10. Sanchez, M. (2009). *Liberal Multiculturalism and the Problems of Difference in the Canadian*.
- Almond, G., and Verba, S. (1989). *The civic culture revisited*.
- Sanchez, M. (2009). *Liberal Multiculturalism and the Problems of Difference in the Canadian Experience*.

¹⁴ Legal bases of the minority policy, 2013.